

The survey questions

Which country do you currently work in?

What's your current primary role/position?

- Full professor
- Assistant / Associate Professor
- Lecturer
- Postdoctoral fellow
- PhD candidate
- Undergraduate student
- Research director / VP of research
- Middle or senior management
- Project manager
- Research scientist
- Clinician / MD
- Consultant / Advisor
- Independent researcher
- Technician
- Other (please specify)

What's your current primary employment status?

- Employed full-time on a permanent contract
- Employed full-time on a temporary contract
- Employed part-time on a permanent contract
- Employed part-time on a temporary contract
- Self-financed, e.g., via PhD/Postdoc scholarship
- Student
- Unemployed
- Retired / on leave

How would you describe the nature of the majority of your research in the last year?

- Fundamental/basic research
- Translational/applied research
- None of the above

What field do you currently mainly work in?

- Mathematics
- Computer and information sciences
- Physical sciences
- Chemical sciences
- Earth and related environmental sciences
- Biological sciences
- Other natural sciences
- Civil engineering
- Electrical engineering, electronic engineering, information engineering
- Mechanical engineering
- Chemical engineering
- Materials engineering
- Medical engineering
- Environmental engineering
- Systems engineering
- Environmental biotechnology
- Industrial biotechnology
- Nano technology
- Other engineering and technologies
- Basic medicine
- Clinical medicine
- Health sciences
- Health biotechnology
- Other medical sciences
- Agriculture, forestry, and fisheries
- Animal and dairy science
- Veterinary science
- Agricultural biotechnology
- Other agricultural sciences
- Psychology
- Economics and business
- Educational sciences
- Sociology
- Law
- Political science
- Social and economic geography
- Media and communications
- Other social sciences
- History and archaeology
- Languages and literature
- Philosophy, ethics and religion

- Arts (arts, history of arts, performing arts, music)
- Other humanities
- Outside of science

In the last twelve months, what percentage of your time at work did you spend on the following duties? (all responses need to add up to 100)

- Research (carrying out or overseeing research, supervising (doctoral) students, finding & reading papers)
- Applying for funding (writing / co-writing grants)
- Publishing (writing & co-writing, peer-review, data storage, sharing)
- Teaching
- Administrative duties
- Other

Looking back over the last 12 months, do you feel like you spent too much, too little, or the right amount of time on the following areas? (*Too little, About right, Too much*)

- My ability to contribute to science
- Other aspects of my work, such as administrative duties or teaching
- My private/family life

In the last 12 months, how satisfied have you been with the following...? (*Very satisfied, Satisfied, Neutral, Dissatisfied, Very dissatisfied*)

- Available research facilities and equipment for your research work
- Funding for research projects available at your institution (excluding third-party funding)
- Available third-party funding opportunities?

To what extent are you free to develop and pursue your own research and teaching agendas without interference by non-academic actors?

- Fully free
- Mostly free
- Moderately restricted
- Severely restricted
- Completely restricted

To what extent are you free to pursue your personal research interests with the funding you have available?

- Fully free
- Mostly free
- Moderately restricted
- Severely restricted
- Completely restricted

What best describes your current primary employment sector?

- Academia
- Industry
- Clinical
- Non-profit
- Government / Public service
- Other (please specify)

What best describes the immediate next career milestone you are working towards?

- Finishing a degree
- A promotion
- Higher salary or merit pay
- A new position at my current employer
- A new position with a different employer
- A new position in a different sector
- Tenure
- Leading my own research group or lab
- Being published in a highly reputable journal
- Other (please specify)

How international or local is the professional peer community that you want to advance your career in?

- Highly international
- Somewhat international
- Balanced between national and international
- More national/local
- Exclusively national/local

In order to reach your next career milestone, which part of your professional peer community is more important for you to connect with?

- The international community
- Both the international and national communities
- The national community

What gender do you identify with?

- Prefer not to answer
- Female
- Male
- Transgender female
- Transgender male
- Gender variant / Non-conforming
- Not listed (enter)

What is the highest degree you have earned?

- PhD (or equivalent)
- Doctor of Medicine (or equivalent)
- Master's (or equivalent)
- Bachelor's (or equivalent)
- No degree yet
- Other (please specify)